

Structural and Vibrational Study of Species Derived from Non-Steroidal Anti-inflammatory Agent Piroxicam Using DFT and Harmonic Force Fields Calculations

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Abstract:

In this investigation, structures of freebase or neutral, anionic, cationic and zwitterionic species of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory piroxicam agent have been optimised in gas phase and aqueous solution by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations in order to predict structural, electronic, topological and vibrational properties for all the species. The solvation energies follow the tendency: cation > anion > zwitterion > neutral. The neutral species presents low hydration and higher stabilities in both media. The frontier orbitals studies show that the reactivity increase according the following order: neutral < cation < anion < zwitterion, thus, the zwitterion is the most reactive species in both media. Very good concordances between experimental and theoretical ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR, IR, Raman and ultraviolet spectra. Complete assignments of all the species and their scaled internal force constants are reported the scaled quantum mechanical force field (SQMFF) methodology.

Keywords: *Piroxicam, Force fields, Molecular structure, Frontier orbital, DFT calculations.*

Introduction

For a long time, our research group has focused on structural and vibrational studies of heterocyclic compounds that have different types of rings in their structures and that are of great medicinal or pharmacological importance (Iramain, et al., 2022; Sundius, & Brandán, 2023). Hence, to report the complete vibrational assignments of different species by combining the infrared and Raman spectra with DFT calculations and the scaled quantum mechanical force field (SQMFF) procedure are our main objective (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). This way, the compounds

are identified in whatever environment due to that all bands observed in the spectra are carefully assigned to vibration modes using the normal internal coordinates and scaling factors. In this work, using that methodology we reported the structural and vibrational study of freebase, anionic, cationic and zwitterion species of piroxicam, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug whose molecular formula is C₁₅H₁₃N₃O₄ (Xu, Rouzer, & Marnett, 2014). Chemically the structure of analgesic agent is 4-Hydroxy-2-methyl-N-2-pyridyl-2H-1,2-benzothiazine-3-carboxamide 1,1-dioxide. The identifications of those species of piroxicam are very important taking into account that only the neutral or

freebase forms are suggested to be medically active and, that in different solvents polymorphic structures depending of pH can be observed (Taddei, Torreggiani, & Simoni, 2001; Mishnev, & Kiselovs, 2013; Kojič-Prodič, & Ružič-Toroš, 1982; Sheth, et al., 2004). So far, some theoretical structural and vibrational studies on piroxicam and its polymorphism (Taddei, Torreggiani, & Simoni, 2001; Suresh, Gunasekaran, & Srinivasan, 2015) were published but the complete and detailed vibrational assignments by using the SQMFF methodology were not reported yet. Hence, to achieve our purposes, the four species of piroxicam have been optimized in gas phase and aqueous solution by using hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations (Becke, 1988; Lee, Yang, & Parr, 1988). Then, the predicted IR, Raman, ^1H , ^{13}C -NMR and UV-Vis spectra were obtained in order to compare with the corresponding experimental ones (Vrečer, Vrbinc, & Meden, 2003; El-Shwiniy, 2020; Kinal, et al., 2019; Studocu, n.d.; SpectraBase, n.d.). After that, the properties, reactivities and behaviours in the

different media were carefully analysed. Finally, the complete assignments of all bands observed in the IR and Raman spectra and the scaled force constants in both media are reported for first time.

Computational Details

The initial theoretical freebase or neutral structure of piroxicam was taken of that experimental CIF file determined by Kojič-Prodič and Ružič-Toroš by using X-ray diffraction (Kojič-Prodič, & Ružič-Toroš, 1982). Then, from that optimized neutral structure in gas phase using the Gaussian 16 program the remaining anionic, cationic and zwitterionic species were built with the *GaussView* program (Dennington, Keith, & Millam, 2019; Frisch, et al. 2019). We can see the structures of all species in Figure 1 together with the identifications of three rings and atoms numbering. Thus, R1 corresponds to benzyl ring, R2 to thiazine ring and R3 to pyridyl ring.

Figure 1. Molecular Structures of Freebase, Anionic, Cationic and Zwitterionic Species of Piroxicam with Definition of Rings and Atoms Numbering

We performed all calculations in solution using the self-consistent reaction field (SCRF) method and the integral equation formalism variant polarised continuum (IEFPCM) model while with the universal solvation model and the

Moldraw program are predicted solvation energies and variations of volumes of species at the same level of theory (Miertus, Scrocco, & Tomasi, 1981; Tomasi, & Persico, 1994; Marenich, Cramer, & Truhlar, 2009; Ugliengo,

1998). Harmonic force fields of species are calculated with the Molvib program and the SQMFF methodology using the corresponding normal internal coordinates and transferable scaling factors (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). Different atomic natural population (NPA) and Merz-Kollman (MK) charges, natural bond orbital (NBO) and atoms in molecules (AIM) calculations are used to predict structural, topological properties and possible intra-molecular interactions (Glendening, et al., 1996; Bader, 1990; Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001; Besler, Merz Jr., & Kollman, 1990) while the frontier orbitals and some descriptors are used to predict reactivities and behaviours of all species of piroxicam (SpectraBase, n.d.; Pearson, 1986; Parr, von Szentpaly, & Liu, 1999). Moreover, comparisons between experimental and predicted ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR and ultraviolet-visible spectra in aqueous solution by using gauge-invariant LCAO (linear combination of atomic orbitals) method (Ditchfield, 1974) and Time-

dependent DFT calculations (TD-DFT) at the same level of theory with the Gaussian 16 program (Frisch, et al. 2019). Finally, better correlations are observed when the Raman of all species predicted in activities are transformed to intensities using suitable equations (Keresztury, et al., 1993).

Results and Discussion

Optimizations in Both Media

The structures of all the species studied of piroxicam are presented in Figure 1 while in Table 1 are summarized the calculated total energies, dipole moments, volume variation and solvation energy for all species in gas phase and aqueous solution by using hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations. The solvation energies are also presented in the table.

Table 1. Comparison of Calculated Total Energies (E), Dipole Moments (μ), Volume Variations (ΔV) and Solvation Energies (ΔG) of the Different Forms of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution

B3LYP/6-31G*				
Piroxicam				
Gas phase				
Species	E (Hartrees)	μ (D)	V (\AA^3)	
Anionic	-1442.2355	4.27	311.2	
Neutral	-1442.7602	4.10	306.8	
Zwitterion	-1442.7102	10.20	314.3	
Cationic	-1443.1170	10.95	309.6	
PCM				
	E (Hartrees)	μ (D)	V (\AA^3)	ΔV (\AA^3)
Anionic	-1442.3360	8.00	309.7	-1.5
Neutral	-1442.7865	6.75	307.1	0.3
Zwitterion	-1442.7864	19.07	310.6	-3.7
Cationic	-1443.2198	16.80	309.8	0.2
Solvation energy (kJ/mol)				
	$\Delta G_u^\#$	ΔG_{ne}	ΔG_c	
Anionic	-263.61	24.70	-288.31	
Neutral	-68.98	22.57	-91.55	
Zwitterion	-199.87	31.89	-231.76	
Cationic	-269.64	30.05	-299.69	

Note: $\Delta G_u^\#$, See text

Regarding the E values, it is observed that the cationic species present the most negative values due to the presence of additional H atoms and, hence, these are the most stable ones while the zwitterion and the neutral species have the same values in solution but slightly different in gas phase. However, the dipole moments values of these two species are completely different in both media showing higher values the zwitterion in solution, as expected due to the separation of charges that present this form. In relation to the volumes, it is observed that the zwitterion and anion present higher values in the gas phase while in solution the anion, cation and zwitterion species show high values. Analysing the volume variations, the zwitterion presents the higher change in solution. Important results are obtained when the positions and orientations of

dipole moments vectors of all species in both media are analysed from Figure 2. Thus, the vectors of anion in the two media are located on N6 in directions to the S1=O3 bonds while in solution an increase in the magnitude it is observed. In the neutral or freebase species in both media, the vectors are located on C11 in direction axial to rings increasing the value in solution. In the zwitterion, the vector in gas phase is located on H31 of N7-H31 bond in direction equatorial to R3 ring but in solution, the vector undergoes a slight shifting in the same direction increasing in significant form its value. In the cation, the vectors are located on N7-C19 bonds in equatorial form in direction to R3 ring but in solution the vector undergoes a slight shifting with increase in its magnitude.

Figure 2. Positions and Orientations of Dipole Moment Vectors for the Four Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Level of Theory

The different behaviours of dipole moments vectors of all the species show that in solution different properties could be expected in both media including different hydrations. Thus, when the solvation energies are analysed from Table 1, we observed that the cationic species presents the most negative value while the neutral species the less negative one. Hence, the following tendency is observed: cation > anion > zwitterion > neutral or freebase, as expected due to that the charged species are most hydrated in solution. Here, the uncorrected (ΔG_{un}) solvation energies are calculated as the differences between E in solution and E gas phase. For instance, the value of $\Delta G_{un}^{\#}$ for the anion -68.98 kJ/mol is calculated from $\Delta G_{un} = [-1442.7865 - (-1442.7602)] \times 627.51 \times 4.18 = -68.98$ kJ/mol. Then, using the energy of the non-electrostatic terms due to the cavitation, dispersion and repulsion energies ΔG_{ne} calculated from PCM calculations, the ΔG_e , is -91.55 kJ/mol. The solvation energy obtained for

the anion is similar to predicted for the freebase of heroin alkaloid (-88.67 kJ/mol) by using B3LYP/6-31G* calculations although its cationic species presents a higher value (-323.14 kJ/mol) than the corresponding to piroxicam (Brandán, 2018). The comparisons of solvation energies with that alkaloid is very important taking into account that the piroxicam species have the N-CH₃ groups, as all tropane alkaloids. Probably, the higher solvation energy observed for heroin than anti-inflammatory piroxicam supports the multiple biological properties of heroin used in medicine for the treatment of severe pain.

Geometrical Parameters in Both Media

Table 2 shows comparisons of calculated geometrical parameters for all species of piroxicam in gas phase and aqueous solution by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method with the corresponding experimental ones reported for the compound by Kojič-Prodič and Ružič-Toroš by using x-ray diffraction (Kojič-Prodič, & Ružič-Toroš, 1982).

Table 2. Comparison of Calculated Geometrical Parameters for All Forms of Piroxicam in Gas and Aqueous Solution Phases Compared with the Corresponding Experimental Ones

Parameters	B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a								Exp ^b
	Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic		
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	
Bond lengths (Å)									
S1-O2	1.460	1.472	1.454	1.468	1.463	1.471	1.456	1.467	1.425
S1-O3	1.470	1.471	1.458	1.466	1.464	1.470	1.454	1.465	1.427
S1-N6	1.682	1.673	1.701	1.686	1.701	1.678	1.718	1.689	1.642
S1-C9	1.795	1.783	1.795	1.785	1.795	1.785	1.797	1.786	1.749
N6-C14	1.478	1.486	1.483	1.490	1.482	1.487	1.487	1.491	1.480
N6-C11	1.457	1.455	1.436	1.441	1.452	1.453	1.437	1.439	1.427
C12-O4	1.241	1.266	1.332	1.340	1.228	1.259	1.323	1.335	1.341
C16-O5	1.228	1.247	1.246	1.252	1.218	1.240	1.231	1.241	1.239
N7-H31	1.012	1.013	1.014	1.014	1.019	1.016	1.020	1.017	0.837
N7-C16	1.423	1.388	1.362	1.358	1.488	1.417	1.413	1.381	1.352
N7-C19	1.376	1.393	1.405	1.405	1.328	1.360	1.359	1.375	1.408
N8-C19	1.349	1.346	1.337	1.340	1.375	1.362	1.364	1.357	1.317
N8-C22	1.333	1.338	1.334	1.338	1.367	1.355	1.362	1.352	-

C11-C12	1.423	1.412	1.372	1.371	1.441	1.419	1.383	1.375	1.369
C11-C16	1.448	1.452	1.469	1.468	1.419	1.437	1.444	1.458	1.461
C10-C12	1.536	1.518	1.471	1.470	1.529	1.516	1.467	1.470	1.461
C10-C9	1.400	1.403	1.405	1.406	1.402	1.404	1.409	1.407	1.397
C10-C15	1.400	1.399	1.400	1.400	1.398	1.398	1.400	1.400	1.399
C19-C20	1.415	1.404	1.401	1.400	1.425	1.406	1.407	1.397	1.387
O4-H36	-	-	0.998	0.996	-	-	0.986	0.991	0.814
N8-H37(36')	-	-	-	-	1.013	1.017	1.015	1.019	-
RMSD^b	0.060	0.054	0.062	0.062	0.073	0.058	0.066	0.063	
Bond angles (°)									
O3-S1-O2	118.8	117.3	120.9	118.2	118.9	117.4	121.3	118.4	119.3
S1-N6-C11	114.5	112.8	112.9	112.3	112.9	112.3	111.5	112.3	113.0
S1-N6-C14	114.9	115.3	115.7	115.4	114.9	115.2	115.2	115.3	115.6
C11-N6-C14	115.8	115.8	115.5	115.2	115.5	115.8	115.3	115.2	116.4
C12-C11-N6	119.9	120.1	121.7	121.2	119.9	120.2	121.9	121.5	120.3
C12-C11-C16	123.7	124.1	119.9	120.6	122.1	123.4	119.7	120.5	121.1
O4-C12-C10	115.7	116.1	114.9	114.8	117.7	116.8	115.3	114.8	115.2
O5-C16-N7	120.5	121.1	123.6	123.5	118.5	120.1	122.2	122.7	123.7
C16-N7-C19	129.3	130.5	129.7	130.1	127.1	128.6	127.5	127.8	129.7
N7-C19-N8	114.2	113.1	112.6	112.7	117.6	115.5	116.5	115.3	112.8
C20-C19-N8	121.8	122.3	123.4	123.1	116.5	117.2	117.5	118.1	123.8
C16-N7-H31	116.0	115.3	116.2	115.8	110.9	114.0	111.3	114.7	117.9
C12-O4-H36	-	-	106.3	106.3	-	-	108.8	107.4	102.4
RMSD^b	1.59	1.60	1.39	1.38	3.74	2.78	3.48	2.53	
Dihedral angles (°)									
C9-S1-N6-C14	81.0	78.7	83.0	80.9	79.7	77.9	79.4	81.0	81.9
O3-S1-N6-C11	-170.0	-173.1	-167.5	-169.8	-170.1	-173.1	-169.0	-169.5	-170.8
N6-C11-C16-N7	8.0	7.0	7.9	6.8	10.2	5.2	9.8	7.9	5.9
S1-N6-C11-C16	-128.7	-129.0	-135.2	-136.1	-117.0	-127.5	-126.3	-135.6	-139.1
C11-C16-N7-C19	-177.5	179.6	-179.4	-177.7	167.6	-179.1	174.0	-179.6	-177.9
O5-C16-N7-C19	2.2	-0.02	0.8	3.0	-9.5	1.3	-3.4	1.5	-2.4
O4-C12-C11-N6	172.1	176.1	177.9	178.6	167.6	174.5	177.5	178.5	179.6
RMSD^b	5.23	135.19	2.58	2.45	130.97	5.31	133.11	2.33	

Note: ^aThis work. ^b Kojić-Prodić, & Ružič-Toroš, 1982 for piroxicam, Bold letters, rmsd values.

The root mean square deviation (RMSD) values are used for all the comparisons, thus, better correlations for the bond lengths and angles of both forms in the two media are observed with the corresponding experimental ones (Kojić-Prodić, & Ružič-Toroš, 1982), showing better concordances in the distances the anion in both

media (0.060-0.054 Å) while the neutral species present the same RMSD values in both media (0.062 Å) but different from the other zwitterion (0.073-0.058 Å) and cation (0.066-0.063 Å). Here, the very important results are related to the lower RMSD values evidenced for all species in solution, showing higher differences between

them the zwitterion (0.015 Å). Analysing the bond angles, the anion (1.59-1.60 °) and neutral species (1.39-1.38 °) show the lower RMSD values while the zwitterion (3.74-2.78 °) and the cation (3.48-2.53 °) the higher values. Examining carefully the RMSD values, the neutral species shows practically the same values in both media indicating that this form is less hydrated in water due to its lower solvation energy, low volume and dipole moment, as compared with the other ones. When the dihedral angles are analysed from Table 2 the better correlations are observed for the neutral species (2.58-2.45 °) and the cation in solution (133.11-2.33 °). Note that the cation presents a great variation from the gas phase to solution while on the contrary is observed for the anion (5.23-135.19 °). Such variations are justified by the changes of signs of dihedral C11-C16-N7-C19 angles of anion and zwitterion. The very good correlations in the bond lengths and angles for all the species suggest that its structures can be used to perform the vibrational analyses and their complete assignments using the harmonic force fields

calculated from SQMFF methodology (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002).

Charges, Molecular Electrostatic Potentials and Bond Orders Studies

The studies of atomic charges are very important for all the species of piroxicam due to the presence in its structures of acceptors (N, O, S atoms) and donor's (O-H, N-H) groups of H bonds that influence on the structural, electronic and topological properties in addition to the biological activities. Thus, atomic natural population (NPA), Merz-Kollman (MK) and Mulliken charges together with the molecular electrostatic potentials (MEP) and bond orders (BO) for all the forms of piroxicam are studied in this section. In Tables 3 and 4 are shown the MK and Mulliken charges on all atoms of those species while in Table 5 the values of NPA charges. Figures 3 and 4 show only the variations of MK, Mulliken and NPA charges, respectively on atoms corresponding to the main acceptors and donor's H bonds groups.

Table 3. Atomic MK Charges (Atomic Units) for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Atoms	MK charges							
	Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic	
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM
1 S	0.913	0.922	0.988	0.984	0.869	0.924	0.968	0.980
2 O	-0.527	-0.590	-0.504	-0.573	-0.517	-0.580	-0.492	-0.564
3 O	-0.558	-0.569	-0.512	-0.548	-0.513	-0.555	-0.467	-0.536
4 O	-0.601	-0.740	-0.548	-0.610	-0.540	-0.711	-0.512	-0.597
5 O	-0.648	-0.743	-0.657	-0.699	-0.588	-0.697	-0.584	-0.657
6 N	-0.068	-0.063	-0.169	-0.137	-0.118	-0.114	-0.286	-0.169
7 N	-0.942	-0.886	-0.896	-0.843	-0.729	-0.761	-0.685	-0.806
8 N	-0.812	-0.832	-0.761	-0.794	-0.413	-0.392	-0.395	-0.391
9 C	-0.011	-0.035	-0.046	-0.082	-0.008	-0.044	-0.107	-0.076
10 C	0.046	0.002	0.135	0.132	0.007	0.001	0.178	0.126
11 C	-0.538	-0.610	-0.307	-0.350	-0.513	-0.621	-0.332	-0.395
12 C	0.506	0.591	0.265	0.322	0.550	0.628	0.324	0.375
13 C	-0.161	-0.141	-0.169	-0.126	-0.130	-0.126	-0.093	-0.127
14 C	-0.323	-0.332	-0.371	-0.335	-0.305	-0.334	-0.286	-0.316
15 C	-0.133	-0.155	-0.149	-0.150	-0.128	-0.151	-0.172	-0.159
16 C	0.897	0.930	0.854	0.865	0.804	0.911	0.789	0.895
17 C	-0.162	-0.130	-0.084	-0.093	-0.147	-0.130	-0.109	-0.079
18 C	-0.131	-0.102	-0.135	-0.117	-0.092	-0.099	-0.080	-0.122
19 C	1.184	1.139	1.149	1.121	0.771	0.776	0.725	0.828
20 C	-0.727	-0.761	-0.723	-0.729	-0.414	-0.467	-0.402	-0.450
21 C	0.250	0.259	0.255	0.257	0.087	0.140	0.116	0.141
22 C	0.405	0.398	0.398	0.397	0.041	0.088	0.074	0.123

23 C	-0.601	-0.543	-0.524	-0.515	-0.277	-0.272	-0.221	-0.254
24 H	0.146	0.162	0.167	0.168	0.155	0.162	0.170	0.172
25 H	0.133	0.170	0.166	0.184	0.143	0.174	0.158	0.182
26 H	0.088	0.122	0.119	0.130	0.111	0.134	0.123	0.135
27 H	0.127	0.137	0.177	0.161	0.126	0.144	0.163	0.159
28 H	0.126	0.148	0.159	0.173	0.137	0.149	0.173	0.182
29 H	0.118	0.146	0.134	0.151	0.133	0.149	0.160	0.153
30 H	0.111	0.1386	0.142	0.154	0.121	0.142	0.152	0.161
31 H	0.351	0.3287	0.364	0.341	0.303	0.362	0.337	0.392
32 H	0.269	0.2813	0.282	0.287	0.243	0.253	0.253	0.262
33 H	0.063	0.0946	0.084	0.101	0.131	0.138	0.150	0.146
34 H	0.033	0.0622	0.057	0.066	0.156	0.182	0.175	0.180
35 H	0.175	0.2000	0.190	0.205	0.174	0.192	0.190	0.196
36 H	-	-	0.467	0.501	-	-	0.462	0.499
37 H	-	-	-	-	0.367	0.404	0.383	0.410

Table 4. Atomic Mulliken Charges (Atomic Units) for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Atoms	Mulliken charges							
	Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic	
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM
1 S	0.857	0.923	0.989	0.984	0.869	0.924	0.968	0.981
2 O	-0.092	-0.590	-0.504	-0.574	-0.517	-0.580	-0.492	-0.564
3 O	-0.231	-0.569	-0.512	-0.548	-0.513	-0.555	-0.467	-0.536
4 O	-0.322	-0.740	-0.548	-0.610	-0.540	-0.711	-0.512	-0.597
5 O	-0.331	-0.743	-0.658	-0.699	-0.588	-0.697	-0.584	-0.657
6 N	-0.018	-0.063	-0.169	-0.137	-0.118	-0.114	-0.286	-0.169
7 N	-0.167	-0.886	-0.896	-0.843	-0.730	-0.761	-0.685	-0.806
8 N	-0.050	-0.832	-0.761	-0.794	-0.413	-0.392	-0.395	-0.391
9 C	-0.582	-0.035	-0.046	-0.082	-0.008	-0.044	-0.108	-0.076
10 C	0.674	0.002	0.135	0.132	0.007	0.001	0.178	0.126
11 C	-0.492	-0.610	-0.307	-0.350	-0.513	-0.621	-0.332	-0.395
12 C	-0.873	0.591	0.265	0.322	0.550	0.628	0.324	0.375
13 C	0.186	-0.141	-0.169	-0.126	-0.131	-0.126	-0.093	-0.127
14 C	-0.358	-0.332	-0.371	-0.335	-0.305	-0.334	-0.286	-0.316
15 C	-0.033	-0.155	-0.149	-0.151	-0.128	-0.151	-0.172	-0.159
16 C	-0.259	0.930	0.855	0.865	0.805	0.912	0.789	0.895
17 C	-0.180	-0.130	-0.084	-0.093	-0.147	-0.130	-0.109	-0.079
18 C	-0.515	-0.102	-0.135	-0.117	-0.092	-0.099	-0.080	-0.122
19 C	-0.389	1.139	1.149	1.121	0.771	0.776	0.725	0.829
20 C	0.739	-0.761	-0.723	-0.729	-0.414	-0.467	-0.402	-0.450
21 C	-0.714	0.259	0.255	0.257	0.087	0.140	0.116	0.141
22 C	-0.137	0.398	0.398	0.397	0.041	0.088	0.074	0.123
23 C	-0.027	-0.543	-0.524	-0.515	-0.277	-0.272	-0.222	-0.254
24 H	0.195	0.163	0.168	0.168	0.155	0.162	0.170	0.172
25 H	0.153	0.170	0.167	0.184	0.143	0.174	0.158	0.183
26 H	0.154	0.122	0.119	0.130	0.112	0.134	0.123	0.135
27 H	0.168	0.137	0.177	0.161	0.127	0.144	0.163	0.159
28 H	0.214	0.149	0.159	0.173	0.137	0.149	0.173	0.182
29 H	0.151	0.146	0.134	0.151	0.133	0.149	0.160	0.153
30 H	0.144	0.139	0.143	0.154	0.121	0.142	0.152	0.161
31 H	0.415	0.329	0.364	0.341	0.303	0.362	0.337	0.392
32 H	0.254	0.281	0.282	0.287	0.243	0.253	0.253	0.262
33 H	0.157	0.095	0.084	0.101	0.131	0.138	0.150	0.146
34 H	0.174	0.062	0.057	0.066	0.157	0.182	0.175	0.180

35 H	0.135	0.200	0.190	0.206	0.174	0.192	0.190	0.196
36 H	-	-	0.467	0.501	-	-	0.462	0.499
37 H	-	-	-	-	0.367	0.404	0.383	0.410

Table 5. NPA Charges (Atomic Units) for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Atoms	NPA charges							
	Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic	
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM
1 S	2.229	2.228	2.229	2.233	2.215	2.227	2.219	2.232
2 O	-0.901	-0.945	-0.879	-0.923	-0.911	-0.940	-0.883	-0.919
3 O	-0.942	-0.950	-0.903	-0.927	-0.919	-0.944	-0.881	-0.922
4 O	-0.648	-0.741	-0.663	-0.671	-0.584	-0.705	-0.628	-0.653
5 O	-0.651	-0.724	-0.681	-0.699	-0.624	-0.694	-0.642	-0.665
6 N	-0.758	-1.121	-0.748	-0.743	-0.772	-1.126	-0.765	-0.745
7 N	-0.634	-0.635	-0.601	-0.595	-0.604	-0.614	-0.608	-0.591
8 N	-0.510	-0.527	-0.484	-0.507	-0.506	-0.472	-0.477	-0.455
9 C	-0.260	-0.270	-0.242	-0.251	-0.257	-0.265	-0.237	-0.246
10 C	-0.078	-0.103	-0.104	-0.107	-0.101	-0.107	-0.134	-0.119
11 C	-0.167	0.507	-0.048	-0.047	-0.167	0.512	-0.078	-0.055
12 C	0.437	0.226	0.406	0.409	0.471	0.241	0.460	0.433
13 C	-0.201	-0.193	-0.189	-0.185	-0.195	-0.191	-0.181	-0.182
14 C	-0.358	-0.367	-0.361	-0.362	-0.357	-0.368	-0.363	-0.362
15 C	-0.182	-0.169	-0.155	-0.151	-0.159	-0.163	-0.125	-0.134
16 C	0.639	0.568	0.663	0.666	0.633	0.564	0.663	0.672
17 C	-0.220	-0.190	-0.175	-0.168	-0.188	-0.183	-0.146	-0.160
18 C	-0.183	-0.183	-0.181	-0.173	-0.184	-0.180	-0.176	-0.178
19 C	0.413	0.397	0.389	0.387	0.472	0.469	0.467	0.463
20 C	-0.276	-0.278	-0.261	-0.263	-0.238	-0.250	-0.238	-0.235
21 C	-0.167	-0.151	-0.148	-0.144	-0.120	-0.091	-0.078	-0.077
22 C	0.056	0.060	0.069	0.064	0.076	0.112	0.102	0.124
23 C	-0.310	-0.283	-0.261	-0.259	-0.270	-0.254	-0.237	-0.233
24 H	0.222	0.235	0.239	0.244	0.232	0.236	0.245	0.244
25 H	0.202	0.214	0.206	0.218	0.203	0.214	0.204	0.219
26 H	0.177	0.190	0.187	0.199	0.189	0.193	0.198	0.201
27 H	0.208	0.214	0.227	0.223	0.215	0.217	0.232	0.225
28 H	0.234	0.232	0.233	0.237	0.238	0.233	0.242	0.243
29 H	0.196	0.222	0.215	0.228	0.209	0.223	0.227	0.229
30 H	0.194	0.219	0.214	0.227	0.208	0.221	0.227	0.228
31 H	0.417	0.415	0.430	0.432	0.423	0.429	0.435	0.441
32 H	0.258	0.248	0.251	0.249	0.284	0.271	0.280	0.270
33 H	0.194	0.216	0.210	0.222	0.223	0.235	0.240	0.242
34 H	0.171	0.192	0.190	0.197	0.218	0.240	0.237	0.247
35 H	0.196	0.221	0.214	0.226	0.231	0.246	0.251	0.251
36 H	-	-	0.514	0.515	-	-	0.523	0.518
37 H	-	-	-	-	0.416	0.442	0.426	0.449

Figure 3. Variations Observed on Calculated MK and Mulliken Charges on N, O and S Atoms Corresponding to Anion, Neutral, Zwitterion and Cation of Piroxicam in Both Media by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method

Figure 4. Variations Observed on Calculated NPA Charges on N, O and S Atoms Corresponding to Anion, Neutral, Zwitterion and Cation of Piroxicam in Both Media by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method

The exhaustive analysis of Figure 3 shows the same variations in the MK and Mulliken charges on atoms of all the species in gas phase with exception of anion (line blue) due to that on O and N atoms present less negative values while the C9 shows a most negative value. In solution, all the species show the same variations in the MK and Mulliken charges. Analysing Figure 4, it is observed that NPA charges present behaviours different from the MK and Mulliken ones. However, similar values are observed on atoms of all the species in both media with exception of N6 that in the anion and zwitterion

the values are most negative in solution probably due to these atoms in those two species are linked to CH₃ groups, as shown in Figure 1. In the neutral and cationic species, the N6 is linked to H31.

Regarding the MEP values from Table 6, we observed the classical tendency: S > O > N > C > H due to the different electronegativities of atoms but the values in the species of piroxicam don't show significant changes when the medium change from the gas phase to solution. For instance, the MEPs values on S and O atoms of all the species show increase in solution while

on some N and C atoms are observed slight decreasing in this medium. The cationic species presents the most labile H37 atoms in both media which are linked to N8 (N8-H37) of pyridine ring because it presents lower MEP value in both media, as observed from Table S4. When the mapped MEP surfaces are analysed through of different colorations from Figure 5 we can see those red and blue regions typical of

nucleophilic and electrophilic sites, respectively. Thus, the nucleophilic sites with red colours are observed on the O of SO₂ and C=O groups and N atoms of all the species while blue colours on the positively charged cation and on H atoms. The anion negatively charged shows higher red coloration on surface, as expected. Note that all surfaces presented with green colours represents inert sites where no reactions occur.

Table 6. Molecular Electrostatic Potentials (Atomic Units) for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Atoms	Molecular electrostatic potentials							
	Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic	
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM
1 S	-59.131	-59.145	-59.007	-59.017	-59.028	-59.044	-58.909	-58.920
2 O	-22.493	-22.526	-22.372	-22.401	-22.388	-22.424	-22.272	-22.303
3 O	-22.489	-22.498	-22.368	-22.386	-22.386	-22.404	-22.270	-22.297
4 O	-22.551	-22.605	-22.323	-22.327	-22.432	-22.503	-22.204	-22.224
5 O	-22.545	-22.593	-22.373	-22.381	-22.416	-22.459	-22.244	-22.246
6 N	-18.469	-18.481	-18.336	-18.334	-18.359	-18.360	-18.231	-18.218
7 N	-18.488	-18.503	-18.338	-18.340	-18.332	-18.314	-18.185	-18.155
8 N	-18.513	-18.517	-18.396	-18.403	-18.263	-18.212	-18.135	-18.096
9 C	-14.839	-14.845	-14.714	-14.715	-14.739	-14.759	-14.617	-14.631
10 C	-14.857	-14.872	-14.719	-14.718	-14.758	-14.785	-14.623	-14.632
11 C	-14.884	-14.909	-14.712	-14.712	-14.766	-14.788	-14.602	-14.593
12 C	-14.831	-14.863	-14.665	-14.665	-14.716	-14.758	-14.548	-14.559
13 C	-14.850	-14.842	-14.735	-14.731	-14.759	-14.769	-14.645	-14.659
14 C	-14.844	-14.843	-14.723	-14.716	-14.743	-14.734	-14.625	-14.611
15 C	-14.866	-14.869	-14.739	-14.733	-14.772	-14.794	-14.646	-14.658
16 C	-14.802	-14.833	-14.640	-14.642	-14.676	-14.691	-14.512	-14.497
17 C	-14.852	-14.834	-14.738	-14.728	-14.763	-14.768	-14.650	-14.663
18 C	-14.854	-14.841	-14.740	-14.729	-14.766	-14.775	-14.653	-14.664
19 C	-14.801	-14.813	-14.681	-14.685	-14.619	-14.594	-14.489	-14.463
20 C	-14.880	-14.885	-14.760	-14.762	-14.723	-14.710	-14.599	-14.583
21 C	-14.858	-14.847	-14.748	-14.746	-14.705	-14.677	-14.586	-14.571
22 C	-14.838	-14.829	-14.730	-14.732	-14.661	-14.613	-14.544	-14.513
23 C	-14.870	-14.853	-14.761	-14.758	-14.714	-14.677	-14.599	-14.579
24 H	-1.186	-1.172	-1.074	-1.070	-1.096	-1.102	-0.986	-1.001
25 H	-1.209	-1.202	-1.086	-1.072	-1.106	-1.085	-0.987	-0.958
26 H	-1.215	-1.206	-1.095	-1.082	-1.114	-1.111	-0.997	-0.990
27 H	-1.211	-1.205	-1.092	-1.091	-1.110	-1.098	-0.994	-0.988
28 H	-1.207	-1.214	-1.080	-1.072	-1.114	-1.140	-0.989	-0.999
29 H	-1.184	-1.154	-1.077	-1.062	-1.100	-1.095	-0.994	-1.003
30 H	-1.188	-1.163	-1.079	-1.062	-1.104	-1.103	-0.996	-1.003
31 H	-1.144	-1.155	-0.998	-1.000	-0.983	-0.955	-0.841	-0.804
32 H	-1.216	-1.232	-1.096	-1.100	-1.066	-1.074	-0.942	-0.937
33 H	-1.193	-1.172	-1.088	-1.078	-1.052	-1.025	-0.939	-0.927
34 H	-1.202	-1.184	-1.098	-1.096	-1.018	-0.966	-0.907	-0.876
35 H	-1.192	-1.163	-1.090	-1.080	-1.045	-1.007	-0.937	-0.921
36 H	-	-	-0.964	-0.970	-	-	-0.847	-0.861
37 H	-	-	-	-	-0.929	-0.867	-0.804	-0.755

Figure 5. Calculated Electrostatic Potential Surfaces on the Molecular Surfaces of Anionic, Neutral, Zwitterion and Cationic Species of Piroxicam in Gas phase by Using the by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method. Isodensity Value of 0.005**

Regarding the bond orders (BO), expressed as Wiberg indexes from Table 7, it is observed only slight differences in the BO related to change of medium from the gas phase to the solution. Thus, a slight increase in the BO is observed for the zwitterion from 4.255 in gas phase to 4.258 in solution while the values for this atom in the other species decrease in this medium. On the contrary, the BO of all O atoms in the four species of piroxicam undergoes decreasing in solution while the BO corresponding to the N

atoms in all species show some changes. Thus, in the anion the BO of N6 and N8 decrease in solution while N7 increase the value. In the zwitterion, N6 and N7 decrease while N8 increase when change the medium from gas to solution. These parameters do not show a definite trend when the environment changes. But we do know that the species are hydrated in solution in the sites where the hydrogen bond acceptor and donor groups are found, as revealed by the mapped MEP surfaces.

Table 7. Wiberg Indexes for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Atoms	Wiberg indexes							
	Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic	
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM
1 S	4.261	4.260	4.269	4.253	4.255	4.258	4.265	4.253
2 O	1.668	1.608	1.703	1.635	1.655	1.616	1.697	1.641
3 O	1.606	1.596	1.662	1.624	1.640	1.605	1.695	1.631
4 O	1.951	1.865	2.004	1.992	2.009	1.902	2.057	2.018
5 O	1.957	1.879	1.941	1.915	2.010	1.922	1.983	1.955
6 N	3.038	2.766	3.043	3.045	3.019	2.758	3.014	3.035
7 N	3.274	3.277	3.311	3.318	3.309	3.288	3.281	3.292
8 N	3.070	3.058	3.082	3.067	3.381	3.418	3.412	3.434
9 C	4.004	4.002	4.003	4.001	4.002	4.002	4.002	4.001
10 C	4.005	4.020	4.002	4.001	4.006	4.018	4.001	4.001
11 C	3.856	3.319	3.935	3.933	3.869	3.323	3.925	3.929
12 C	3.952	3.975	3.919	3.917	3.940	3.976	3.902	3.911

13 C	3.961	3.955	3.954	3.951	3.958	3.954	3.950	3.951
14 C	3.832	3.820	3.811	3.797	3.821	3.815	3.803	3.794
15 C	3.955	3.955	3.953	3.950	3.951	3.954	3.944	3.945
16 C	3.902	3.953	3.894	3.893	3.897	3.951	3.890	3.888
17 C	3.970	3.961	3.963	3.957	3.965	3.960	3.955	3.955
18 C	3.966	3.960	3.962	3.956	3.964	3.959	3.956	3.955
19 C	3.955	3.955	3.952	3.951	3.920	3.921	3.919	3.920
20 C	3.939	3.941	3.942	3.942	3.928	3.932	3.928	3.933
21 C	3.969	3.958	3.961	3.955	3.953	3.941	3.935	3.934
22 C	3.956	3.943	3.943	3.939	3.900	3.882	3.884	3.875
23 C	3.959	3.955	3.959	3.955	3.952	3.947	3.945	3.945
24 H	0.954	0.947	0.944	0.942	0.948	0.947	0.943	0.943
25 H	0.962	0.957	0.960	0.954	0.961	0.956	0.960	0.954
26 H	0.972	0.967	0.968	0.963	0.967	0.966	0.963	0.962
27 H	0.959	0.957	0.951	0.952	0.956	0.955	0.948	0.951
28 H	0.949	0.949	0.948	0.946	0.947	0.948	0.943	0.943
29 H	0.964	0.953	0.956	0.950	0.958	0.952	0.950	0.949
30 H	0.965	0.954	0.956	0.950	0.959	0.953	0.951	0.950
31 H	0.829	0.839	0.818	0.817	0.825	0.821	0.815	0.809
32 H	0.936	0.941	0.940	0.941	0.922	0.929	0.924	0.929
33 H	0.965	0.955	0.958	0.953	0.952	0.946	0.944	0.943
34 H	0.974	0.966	0.967	0.963	0.954	0.944	0.945	0.940
35 H	0.964	0.953	0.957	0.951	0.948	0.941	0.939	0.938
36 H	-	-	0.741	0.740	-	-	0.731	0.737
37 H	-	-	-	-	0.830	0.807	0.821	0.800

NBO and AIM Calculations

The studies in solution evidenced that the cationic species of piroxicam (-299.69 kJ/mol) has a solvation energy in water close to the cationic of heroin alkaloid (-323.14 kJ/mol) while the other species with charge, anion (-288.31 kJ/mol) and zwitterion (-231.76 kJ/mol) present lower values and different from the neutral or freebase (-91.55 kJ/mol). Obviously, the species with charge present higher hydration in solution but the stabilities of all species of piroxicam are not known. For this reason, NBO and AIM calculations were performed to know its stabilities in both media using two different methodologies (Glendening, et al., 1996; Bader, 1990; Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001). In the NBO study, the donor-acceptor energy interactions are calculated as E(2) parameters obtained from the second order perturbation theory analysis of Fock matrix with the NBO 3.1 program by using the hybrid

B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory (Glendening, et al., 1996). Thus, in Table 8 are presented the main donor-acceptor energies for all the species of piroxicam in gas phase and aqueous solution by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory. Here, only are presented the final energies of all observed interactions because the complete table presents 15 pages. Thus, the complete table of all observed interactions is available upon request by the authors. Regarding the shortened table we observed a total of ten transitions in all species and in the two media which are the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $\sigma \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\sigma^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $\sigma^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$ interactions but the $\sigma^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition only is observed in the cationic species in gas phase. Besides, the $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $\sigma \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions are not observed in the anion and zwitterion species in gas phase.

Table 8. Main Donor-Acceptor Energy Interactions (in kJ/mol) for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Delocalization	Piroxicam							
	Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic	
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM
$\Delta E(\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*)$	-	139668.56	53035.59	58239.86	-	155665.92	277796.40	350219.04
$\Delta E(\sigma \rightarrow \pi^*)$	-	7062.74	7663.78	40821.96	-	22890.43	15948.33	12049.90
$\Delta E(\pi \rightarrow \sigma^*)$	-	2820.91	8736.24	9287.04	-	34684.05	220.08	5898.02
$\Delta E(\pi \rightarrow \pi^*)$	1036.22	997.77	4616.31	1466.93	874.04	9629.01	1666.02	1131.82
$\Delta E(\sigma^* \rightarrow \sigma^*)$	187.31	171.09	663.37	4693.39	0.00	53.25	46590.78	4333.99
$\Delta E(\sigma^* \rightarrow \pi^*)$	-	-	-	-	-	-	22017.19	-
$\Delta E(\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*)$	-	6627.35	11663.58	13383.06	-	24069.57	30143.40	6876.64
$\Delta E(\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*)$	3569.59	1710.25	4193.42	4278.90	2077.13	5047.48	7137.39	1387.72
$\Delta E(LP \rightarrow \sigma^*)$	762.52	915.09	201934.50	161621.54	946.27	1194.69	5904.63	1083.62
$\Delta E(LP \rightarrow \pi^*)$	1205.85	811.13	336014.23	680055.49	1144.44	1422.91	515.73	992.50
ΔE_{Total}	6761.49	160784.89	628521.02	973848.17	5041.88	254657.31	407939.95	383973.25

A very important results is the strong increase of energies in solution of the transitions corresponding to anion, neutral and zwitterion species, in particular, the anion and zwitterion. However, the cation shows an important diminishing in the E value in solution. All the interactions predicted are related to the charges transfer from bonding orbital S=O, C=C, C=N, OH, NH to antibonding S=O, C=C, C=N, OH, NH some of them correspond to interaction of different rings and to transitions from lone pairs of O and N atoms towards different antibonding σ^* and π^* orbitals. Evaluating the total energies, we observed that the neutral species in the two media present the higher values probably because it is the most stable in both media and the less hydrated in solution. On the other hand, the cation is the less stable species in aqueous solution probably due to its higher solvation energy and, for this reason, this species is most hydrated.

The stabilities of all species of piroxicam were also studied using the theory of atoms in molecules (AIM) by means of the topological properties calculated with the AIM 2000 program (Bader, 1990; Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001). Such properties, electron density, $\rho(r)$, Laplacian values, $\nabla^2\rho(r)$, eigenvalues ($\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$) of the Hessian matrix and, $|\lambda_1|/|\lambda_3|$ ratio are calculated in the bond critical points (BCPs) and ring critical point (RCPs). Thus, in Table 9 are summarized those properties for all species of piroxicam in gas phase and aqueous solution by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory. The molecular graphics for four species in gas phase showing the H bonds and RCPNs are given in Figure 6 while in Figure 7 are shown the molecular graphics for zwitterion species in both media because only for this species are observed changes in solution.

Table 9. Analysis of the Topological Properties for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Gas Phase						
Anionic						
Parameter (a.u.)	N6...H31	RCPN1	O5...H32	RCPN2	O4...O5	RCPN3
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0225	0.0206	0.0202	0.0125	0.0106	0.0105
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.0892	0.1212	0.0744	0.0704	0.0408	0.0452
λ_1	-0.0250	-0.0184	-0.0218	-0.0094	-0.0082	-0.0081
λ_2	-0.0172	0.0243	-0.0201	0.0259	-0.0025	0.0029

λ_3	0.1316	0.1155	0.1163	0.0538	0.0514	0.0505
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.1900	0.1593	0.1874	0.1747	0.1595	0.1604
Distance (Å)	<i>2.164</i>		<i>2.155</i>		<i>2.9187</i>	
Neutral						
Parameter (a.u.)	N6···H31	RCPN1	O5···H32	RCPN2	H36···O5	RCPN3
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0182	0.0179	0.0171	0.0114	0.0546	0.0203
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.0752	0.0940	0.0628	0.0636	0.1472	0.1248
λ_1	-0.0184	-0.0164	-0.0176	-0.0086	-0.0964	-0.0183
λ_2	-0.0088	0.0113	-0.0160	0.0221	-0.0948	0.0657
λ_3	0.1026	0.0991	0.0964	0.0502	0.3384	0.0774
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.1793	0.1655	0.1826	0.1713	0.2849	0.2364
Distance (Å)	<i>2.266</i>		<i>2.236</i>		<i>1.648</i>	
Zwitterion						
Parameter (a.u.)	N6···H31	RCPN1	O5---H32	RCPN2		
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0299	0.0238	0.0205	0.0127		
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.1056	0.1496	0.0764	0.0724		
λ_1	-0.0380	-0.0219	-0.0227	-0.0094		
λ_2	-0.0309	0.0413	-0.0203	0.0262		
λ_3	0.1747	0.1303	0.1194	0.0557		
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2175	0.1681	0.1901	0.1688		
Distance (Å)	<i>2.016</i>		<i>2.139</i>			
Cationic						
Parameter (a.u.)	N6···H31	RCPN1	O5···H32	RCPN2	H36···O5	RCPN3
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0249	0.0218	0.0181	0.0120	0.0401	0.0186
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.0896	0.1292	0.0676	0.0680	0.1268	0.1120
λ_1	-0.0296	-0.0208	-0.0193	-0.0090	-0.0623	-0.0165
λ_2	-0.0226	0.0319	-0.0171	0.0233	-0.0614	0.0527
λ_3	0.1416	0.1179	0.1039	0.0536	0.2505	0.0757
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2090	0.1764	0.1857	0.1679	0.2487	0.2180
Distance (Å)	<i>2.104</i>		<i>2.202</i>		<i>1.772</i>	
Aqueous solution						
Anionic						
Parameter (a.u.)	N6···H31	RCPN1	O5···H32	RCPN2	O4···O5	RCPN3
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0231	0.0210	0.0175	0.0117	0.0125	0.0119
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.0912	0.1244	0.0620	0.0636	0.0432	0.0572
λ_1	-0.0262	-0.0193	-0.0174	-0.0086	-0.0097	-0.0088
λ_2	-0.0187	0.0265	-0.0160	0.0220	-0.0074	0.0110
λ_3	0.1360	0.1175	0.0954	0.0502	0.0604	0.0548
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.1926	0.1642	0.1824	0.1713	0.1606	0.1606
Distance (Å)	<i>2.142</i>		<i>2.247</i>		<i>2.852</i>	
Neutral						
Parameter (a.u.)	N6···H31	RCPN1	O5···H32	RCPN2	H36···O5	RCPN3
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0183	0.0180	0.0165	0.0112	0.0532	0.0200
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.0760	0.0956	0.0596	0.0620	0.1455	0.1220

λ_1	-0.0189	-0.0167	-0.0166	-0.0084	-0.0930	-0.0179
λ_2	-0.0098	0.0127	-0.0151	0.0212	-0.0913	0.0646
λ_3	0.1047	0.0998	0.0915	0.0491	0.3300	0.0754
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.1805	0.1673	0.1814	0.1711	0.2818	0.2374
Distance (Å)	2.248		2.262		1.659	
Zwitterion						
Parameter (a.u.)	N6...H31	RCPN1	O5...H32	RCPN2	O4...O5	RCPN3
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0246	0.0217	0.0182	0.0121	0.0124	0.0120
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.0940	0.1308	0.0656	0.0668	0.0440	0.0568
λ_1	-0.0291	-0.0203	-0.0187	-0.0091	-0.0098	-0.0090
λ_2	-0.0218	0.0305	-0.0170	0.0225	-0.0069	0.0099
λ_3	0.1449	0.1207	0.1015	0.0533	0.0606	0.0559
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2008	0.1682	0.1842	0.1707	0.1617	0.1610
Distance (Å)	2.103		2.218		2.850	
Cationic						
Parameter (a.u.)	N6...H31	RCPN1	O5...H32	RCPN2	H36...O5	RCPN3
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0194	0.0187	0.0163	0.0115	0.0473	0.0193
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.0780	0.1024	0.0600	0.0640	0.1392	0.1176
λ_1	-0.0208	-0.0175	-0.0166	-0.0084	-0.0788	-0.0173
λ_2	-0.0123	0.0167	-0.0142	0.0200	-0.0777	0.0597
λ_3	0.1110	0.1034	0.0907	0.0523	0.2957	0.0752
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.1874	0.1692	0.1830	0.1606	0.2665	0.2301
Distance (Å)	2.217		2.268		1.704	

Figure 6. Molecular Graphics of Anion, Neutral, Zwitterion and Cation Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase Showing Their H Bonds Interactions (BCPs) and Ring Critical Points (RCPs) by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Level of Theory

Figure 7. Molecular Graphics of Zwitterion Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution Showing Their H Bonds Interactions (BCPs) and Ring Critical Points (RCPs) by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Regarding table 9 and figure 6, it is observed three new H bonds interactions in the anion (C12-O4...O5, C16-O5...H32, N7-H31...N6), neutral (C16-O5...H36, C16-O5...H32, N7-H31...N6) and cation (C16-O5...H36, C16-O5...H32, C14-N6...H31) species in both media while for the zwitterion only two interactions are observed in gas phase (C16-O5...H32, N7-H31...N6). On the contrary, in solution other new H bond is observed in the zwitterion which can be described as C12-O4...O5 or its equivalent C16-O5...O4. Note that the new RCPs of rings formed due to the H bonds are presented on the figure 6 as RCPN1, RCPN2 and RCPN3. The analyses of densities of different rings show that the N7-H31...N6 interaction of zwitterion in gas phase and of cation in solution present the higher density values which are respectively 0.0299 and 0.0473 a.u. In general, these NBO and AIM studies suggest that the neutral species presents higher

stabilities in both media while the cation is the less stable species in aqueous solution probably due to its higher hydration.

Frontier Orbitals and Descriptors Studies

The reactivities and behaviours of all species of piroxicam in gas phase and aqueous solution are predicted with the gap energies and some descriptors by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory, as suggested by Parr et al and Pearson (Pearson, 1986; Parr, von Szentpaly, & Liu, 1999) From the differences between HOMO and LUMO are calculated the gap values and some descriptors. Hence, these parameters are shown for all species in Table 10 together with the equations to compute the chemical potential (μ), electronegativity (χ), global hardness (η), global softness (S) and global electrophilicity index (ω) descriptors using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method.

Table 10. Calculated HOMO and LUMO Orbitals, Energy Band Gap, Chemical Potential (μ), Electronegativity (χ), Global Hardness (η), Global Softness (S), Global Electrophilicity Index (ω) and Global Nucleophilicity Index (E) for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Frontier orbitals (eV)	Piroxicam ^a							
	Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic	
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM
HOMO	-2.1632	-5.5232	-6.6569	-6.7263	-5.4660	-5.9146	-9.8994	-7.1918
LUMO	1.2748	-1.7308	-2.5822	-2.6149	-2.9033	-2.4824	-6.3219	-3.1222

GAP	3.4380	3.7924	4.0748	4.1114	2.5627	3.4323	3.5775	4.0696
Descriptors (eV)								
χ	0.4442	3.6270	4.6196	4.6706	4.1846	4.1985	8.1107	5.1570
μ	-0.4442	-3.6270	-4.6196	-4.6706	-4.1846	-4.1985	-8.1107	-5.1570
η	1.0816	2.7616	3.3285	3.3632	2.7330	2.9573	4.9497	3.5959
S	0.4623	0.1811	0.1502	0.1487	0.1830	0.1691	0.1010	0.1390
ω	0.0912	2.3818	3.2057	3.2431	3.2037	2.9803	6.6451	3.6979

Note: ^aThis work, $\chi = -[E(\text{LUMO}) + E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\mu = [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\eta = [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $S = 1/2\eta = \omega^2/2\eta$

In gas phase and aqueous solution, the reactivity increase according to: neutral < cation < anion < zwitterion, thus, the zwitterion is the most reactive species in both media. Here, we remember that a species is reactive when the gap value is low while a high gap value indicates that it is less reactive probably due to that the species presents a higher kinetic stability. The analysis shows clearly that all the species of piroxicam are less reactive in solution because the gap values present higher values than the corresponding in gas phase. Observing with details the descriptors, the global softness (S) for the zwitterion show the lower values. Hence, the higher reactivity that evidence this species in both media can be attributed to this descriptor.

NMR Study

Predicted ¹H and ¹³C-NMR chemical shifts of all species of piroxicam in aqueous solution by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations are compared with the experimental ones for piroxicam in DMSO-d₆ by using the root mean square deviation (RMSD) values (Vrecer, Urbinc, & Meden, 2003; El-Shwiniy, 2020; Kinal, et al., 2019). The concordances between theoretical and experimental spectra would confirm that the structures could be used to perform the vibrational analyses. Hence, calculated ¹H and ¹³C-NMR chemical shifts for all species in aqueous solution compared with the corresponding experimental reported are summarized in Tables 11 and 12 (Vrecer, Urbinc, & Meden, 2003; El-Shwiniy, 2020; Kinal, et al., 2019).

Table 11. Observed and Calculated ¹H Chemical Shifts (δ in ppm) for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

¹ H-NMR ^a							
H Atoms	6-311++G**				Experimental in DMSO-d ₆ ^b		
	Anionic	Neutral	Zwitterion	Cationic	δ ppm	Multiplicity, Integ.	Assignment
H36	-	13.37	-	12.74	-	-	-
H37	-	-	9.79	10.31	-	-	-
H31	9.17	9.07	9.53	9.37	10.52	s, 1 H	-NH
H32	8.68	8.75	9.21	9.17	8.41	d, 2 H	2-pyridine
H34	8.60	8.73	8.29	8.53	8.39		
H33	8.13	8.24	8.58	8.76	8.06		
H35	7.25	7.49	7.50	7.84	7.97	d, 2 H	1-benzene
H28	8.34	8.48	8.36	8.55	7.88		
H24	8.02	8.23	8.04	8.27	7.86		
H30	8.10	8.24	8.13	8.24	7.28	t, 2 H	
H29	8.03	8.21	8.09	8.27	7.26		
H27	3.29	3.34	3.31	3.37	2.51	s, 3 H	-CH ₃

H25	2.96	3.08	2.95	3.04			
H26	2.48	2.51	2.54	2.62			
RMSD	0.63	0.70	0.62	0.71			

Note: ^aThis work GIAO/B3LYP/6-311++G** Ref. to TMS. ^b El-Shwiniy, 2020

Table 12. Observed and Calculated ¹³C Chemical Shifts (δ in ppm) for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

¹³ C-NMR ^a						Exp. ^c
C Atoms	6-311++G**				Exp. ^b	in DMSO-d ₆ ^c
	Anionic	Neutral	Zwitterion	Cationic	δ ppm	
C12	176.9	168.3	179.6	170.6	158.7	158.6
C16	172.6	174.1	170.2	173.7	166.9	167.43
C19	160.7	157.9	153.2	150.6	150.1	150.52
C22	155.3	155.5	144.3	145.8	148.2	148.1
C21	144.4	145.2	153.6	155.5	138.4	138.4
C9	143.3	142.7	143.4	143.1	134.6	135.23
C10	142.9	133.5	141.7	132.4	128.3	128.3
C18	139.4	140.3	139.7	140.5	132.5	133.72
C17	136.5	139.9	137.5	141.0	133.0	133.21
C15	133.1	132.8	133.3	133.5	126.6	127.03
C13	128.4	129.7	128.8	129.9	124.8	124.38
C23	122.1	125.5	122.5	126.5	120.6	120.6
C20	115.1	117.8	119.2	121.7	114.3	116.86
C11	114.3	117.3	114.2	116.6	111.5	111.38
C14	41.5	40.1	41.9	40.5	39.9	40.0
RMSD^b	8.08	6.52	8.69	7.72		
RMSD^c	7.93	6.25	8.49	7.41		

Note: ^aThis work GIAO/B3LYP/6-311++G** Ref. to TMS, ^b Vrečer, Vrbinc, & Meden, 2003, ^c Kinal, et al., 2019

The gauge-invariant LCAO method was used to predict the NMR chemical shifts of all species of piroxicam (Ditchfield, 1974). From Table 11, reasonable correlations for all species show RMSD values between 0.71 and 0.62 ppm. In general, B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations predicted overestimation of some values in relation to the experimental ones. Analysing the correlations in the ¹³C chemical shifts from Table 12 we see that the RMSD values (8.69-7.72 ppm) computed from Kinal, et al., (2019) are slightly lower than those obtained (8.49-7.41 pp) using the Vrečer, Vrbinc, & Meden, (2003) showing, both studies practically similar concordances. Hence, the ¹³C chemical shifts for all the species of piroxicam present slightly higher than the H ones. Such differences could be related to the

B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations because this level of calculation produce better results for the H nuclei than the C ones. In addition, taking into account that the chemical shifts are predicted in aqueous solution instead DMSO deuterated those differences could also be attributed to solvent. The observed correlations RMSDs suggest that the structures of all species can be used to perform the corresponding vibrational studies and assignments by using the SQMFF procedure.

Vibrational Analysis

The hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method optimized the structures of species of piroxicam in the two media with *C_i* symmetries. Then, the presence of 36 atoms in the freebase/neutral and the zwitterion a total of 102 normal vibration

modes are expected while 99 in the anion and 105 in the cation due to their 35 and 37 atoms, respectively. Figures 8 and 9 show comparisons of experimental infrared and Raman spectra of piroxicam in the solid phase with the

corresponding predicted for the anion, neutral, zwitterion and cation in the gas phase by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method (Studocu, n.d.; SpectraBase, n.d.).

Figure 8. Comparisons Between the Experimental Infrared Spectrum of Piroxicam in the Solid Phase with the Corresponding Predicted for the Anion, Neutral, Zwitterion and Cation in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Figure 9. Comparisons Between the Experimental Raman Spectrum of Piroxicam in the Solid Phase with the Corresponding Predicted for the Anion, Neutral, Zwitterion and Cation in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Both spectra show bands due to all the species. The predicted Raman spectra corrected from activities to intensities show better correlations (Keresztury, et al., 1993). In the region of higher wavenumbers, the experimental IR spectrum shows the bands attributed to OH of freebase and the cation and to NH, CH and CH₃ stretching modes of all the species. The normal internal coordinates of all the species and transferable scaling factors allow obtaining the harmonic force fields using the SQMFF methodology and the Molvib program (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). Then, in the assignments of bands observed in

the IR spectra to the normal vibration modes are used PED contributions $\geq 10\%$. Observed and calculated wavenumbers for the anion, neutral or freebase, zwitterion and cation of piroxicam in gas phase and their corresponding assignments are summarized in Table 13. Obviously, different assignments are observed in the anion and zwitterion due to the absence of OH groups and to the absence of NH groups in the pyridyl rings of freebase and anion, as can be seen from Figure 1. Then, discussions of some assignments by regions are presented below.

Table 13. Observed and Calculated Wavenumbers (cm⁻¹) and Assignments for All Species of Piroxicam in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Experimental		B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a							
		Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic	
IR	Raman	SQM ^b	Assignments ^b	SQM ^b	Assignments ^b	SQM ^b	Assignments ^b	SQM ^b	Assignments ^b
3392 s		3434	vN7-H31	3409	vN7-H31	3434	vN8-H36	3415	vN8-H37
3311 m						3311	vN7-H31	3306	vN7-H31
3234 sh								3261	vO4-H36
3178 s				3112	vC20-H32	3102	vC20-H32	3118	vC20-H32
	3094w	3101	vC20-H32			3097	vC22-H34	3100	vC22-H34
						3083	vC23-H35	3089	vC23-H35
3075 sh	3066w			3078	vC15-H28	3067	vC15-H28	3080	vC15-H28
				3069	vC13-H24	3064	vC13-H24	3073	vC13-H24
				3066	vC23-H35			3066	vC21-H33
	3056sh	3059	vC15-H28	3058	vC17-H29	3058	vC21-H33	3065	vC18-H30
		3056	vC13-H24	3046	vC21-H33	3052	vC17-H29	3055	vC17-H29
		3049	vC23-H35	3045	vC18-H30				
	3022w	3038	vC17-H29	3028	vO4-H36	3038	vC18-H30		
		3022	vC21-H33	3026	vC22-H34				
		3020	vC18-H30	3024	v _a CH ₃	3011	v _a CH ₃	3025	v _a CH ₃
	2991 vw	3003	v _a CH ₃	2975	v _a CH ₃	2972	v _a CH ₃	2979	v _a CH ₃
2980 w		2991	vC22-H34						
2909 w	2941 w	2963	v _a CH ₃					2907	v _s CH ₃
2882 w		2874	v _s CH ₃	2894	v _s CH ₃	2895	v _s CH ₃		
1647 s		1657	vC16=O5			1710	vC16=O5; vC11-C16	1664	vC16=O5
1602 m	1612 s	1580	vC20-C21	1614	vC16=O5	1632	vN7-C19	1629	βN8-H37
1592 m	1596 s			1583	vC19-C20	1594	vC22-C23	1607	vN8-C22
1586 m	1576 m	1575	vC13-C17	1578	vC15-C18; vC9-C13	1591	vC12=O4		
1572 s	1565 m	1557	vC9-C10	1567	vC20-C21	1570	vC15-C18; vC9-C13	1573	vC15-C18
				1561	vC17-C18			1557	vC17-C18; vC10-C15
1548 s	1541 vs	1546	vC21-C23	1529	ρN7-C16	1546	vC17-C18; vC13-C17; vC10-C15	1539	vC20-C21
	1520 w	1526	vC12=O4	1522	vC11-C12	1516	vC20-C21		
								1505	ρN7-C16
	1485 w	1490	ρN7-C16			1479	ρN7-C16	1498	vC11-C12
				1456	βC15-H28; βC13-H24			1456	βC13-H24; vC9-C10
				1446	βC22-H34				

1440 s		1440	vC22-C23			1441	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3$	1443	vC9-C10
	1437 s	1437	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3$	1439	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3$	1440	$\beta\text{C13-H24}$		
		1435	$\beta\text{C13-H24}$					1432	$\beta\text{C22-H34};$ $\beta\text{C23-H35}$
		1426	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3$	1428	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3$	1426	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3$	1428	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3$
				1427	$\beta\text{C17-H29}$	1425	$\beta\text{C17-H29};$ $\beta\text{C18-H30}$	1427	$\beta\text{C18-H30}$
1417 s		1419	vC9-C13	1421	$\beta\text{C21-H33}$	1423	$\beta\text{C23-H35}$		
		1408	$\beta\text{C22-H34}$						
		1377	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3$	1388	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3$	1381	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3$	1390	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3$
								1374	$\beta\text{C20-H32}$
	1359 m					1369	$\beta\text{N8-H36}$	1368	vC12-O4
1337 s	1323 m	1337	vC11-C12; vC11-C16	1354	vC10-C12	1354	$\beta\text{C20-H32}$		
1308 s	1313 m			1305	vC10-C12			1320	vN7-C19
		1288	vN7-C19	1292	vC9-C10; vC9-C13	1295	vC11-C12	1293	vC9-C13
		1282	vC10-C15	1280	vN7-C19	1282	vC9-C10; vC10-C15	1280	vC19-C20; vN8-C19
	1278 m	1277	vN8-C22	1273	vN8-C22			1270	$v_a\text{SO}_2$
	1267 sh			1262	$v_a\text{SO}_2$	1255	vN8-C19	1261	$\beta\text{C15-H28}$
	1235 s	1240	$\beta\text{C15-H28}$	1249	$\delta\text{O4-H362};$ vC10-C15	1246	$\beta\text{C15-H28}$	1232	vC11-C16
1231 w		1228	vN8-C19	1235	vN6-C11	1224	$v_a\text{SO}_2$	1229	$\delta\text{O4-H36}$
	1221 m	1221	$v_a\text{SO}_2$	1215	vN8-C19	1213	$\beta\text{C22-H34}$	1224	vN6-C11
1172 vs	1185 m	1183	vN6-C11	1194	$q\text{CH}_3$	1196	vN6-C11; vC11-C16	1182	vC10-C12
1158 m	1164 s	1158	$q\text{CH}_3$	1155	$\beta\text{C18-H30}$	1164	$q\text{CH}_3$	1162	$\beta\text{C21-H33};$ $\beta\text{C23-H35}$
		1145	$\beta\text{C18-H30}$			1151	$\beta\text{C17-H29};$ $\beta\text{C18-H30}$	1161	$\beta\text{C17-H29}$
				1150	vC12-O4	1151	$\beta\text{C21-H33}$		
1137 m	1138 sh	1138	$\beta\text{C17-H29}$					1149	$q\text{CH}_3$
	1132 w	1132	$\beta\text{C21-H33}$	1142	$\beta\text{C20-H32}$	1141	vC10-C12	1118	$q\text{CH}_3$
1118m		1112	$q'\text{CH}_3$	1127	vN7-C16				
				1112	vC9-S1	1115	$q'\text{CH}_3$	1114	vC13-C17
	1099 w	1097	vC9-S1	1107	$q'\text{CH}_3$	1102	vC13-C17	1097	vN8-C22
				1089	$v_s\text{SO}_2$	1087	vN8-C22	1092	$v_s\text{SO}_2$
		1081	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1})$			1080	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1})$		
1076 w		1076	$\beta\text{C23-H35}$	1083	$\beta\text{C23-H35}$				
1058 m	1051 m	1054	vN7-C16	1040	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1})$			1065	vN7-C16
1031 m		1030	$v_s\text{SO}_2$	1031	vC21-C23; vC22-C23	1031	$v_s\text{SO}_2$	1039	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1})$
		1022	$\beta\text{C20-H32}$			1027	vN6-C14	1027	$\gamma\text{C21-H33}$
								1020	vC21-C23

				1019	vC13-C17	1017	γ C21-H33	1016	vC17-C18; vC13-C17; vC15-C18
		1009	vC17-C18; vC15-C18	1010	vN6-C14	1009	vC17-C18	1012	γ C18-H3
		1001	vN6-C14	1004	γ C21-H33	1004	β R ₁ (A3); vC21-C23	1005	vN6-C14
	993 s	990	γ C21-H33	1001	γ C18-H30	999	γ C15-H28	991	β R ₁ (A3)
		984	γ C15-H28; γ C18-H30	988	β R ₁ (A3)	995	β R ₁ (A3); vC21-C23		
		981	β R ₁ (A3)	972	γ C22-H34			980	γ C15-H28
952 vw		953	γ C17-H29	971	γ C13-H24	969	γ C17-H29	971	γ C15-H2
						956	β C11-C16		
	943 vw	947	γ C22-H34			946	γ C22-H34		
		904	β C12-O4	927	ρ C16-C11			910	β C12-O4
882 m		881	γ C20-H32	898	γ C20-H32	888	γ C13-H24	896	γ C13-H24
	876 w	877	γ C13-H24	890	γ C15-H28	877	γ C20-H32	893	γ C20-H32
833 s	826 w	851	vC19-C20	859	δ C16N7C19	864	vC19-C20	851	δ C16N7C19
				808	γ C16-C11	818	δ C16N7C19; δ C11C16N7	799	γ C16-C11
				792	τ O4-H36				
		789	γ C12-O4	784	γ C23-H35	790	γ C12=O4	790	γ C23-H35
	776 w	776	vN6-S1	783	τ R ₁ (A2)			781	γ C17-H29
765 s		765	γ C23-H35	767	γ C17-H29	761	γ C23-H35	772	γ C16-C11; γ C17-H29
						759	γ C18-H30		
		756	vC10-C12	752	vN6-S1	753	β R ₃ (A1)	752	vN6-S1
		751	γ C16-C11	750	τ R ₁ (A3); γ N7-H31; γ C21-H33	750	vN6-S1		
745 m	741 vw	741	γ C18-H30	740	τ R ₁ (A1)	744	τ R ₁ (A1); β R ₃ (A1);	741	τ R ₁ (A2)
		738	τ R ₁ (A3)					733	γ N8-H37
		720	β R ₃ (A1)	724	β R ₃ (A1); vC9-S1	717	γ C16-C11	722	β R ₃ (A1)
		704	γ N7-H31			709	τ R ₁ (A3); ρ C16-C11	706	γ C19-N7
						698	γ C19-N7	704	τ O4-H36
671 m	666 w	668	τ R ₁ (A1)	723	τ R ₁ (A3)	668	τ R ₁ (A1)	672	τ R ₁ (A1)
				659	γ C12-O4	651	β R ₂ (A1)	655	γ C12-O4
650 m		654	β R ₂ (A1)	656	β R ₂ (A1)	643	γ CN8-H36	650	β R ₂ (A1)
632 m	631 vw	632	β R ₂ (A3)	633	β R ₂ (A3); β R ₃ (A3)	626	β R ₂ (A3); β R ₃ (A3)	630	β R ₂ (A3)
615 sh		618	β R ₁ (A2)	613	wagSO ₂	620	β R ₁ (A2)	614	β R ₃ (A3)
602 m	588 w	575	wagSO ₂	571	τ R ₂ (A1)	574	wagSO ₂	569	wagSO ₂
565 s	563 vw	552	β R ₃ (A3)	560	β R ₁ (A2)	551	β R ₃ (A3); ρ C16-C11	560	β R ₁ (A2)
	535 vw	544	δ SO ₂	547	δ SO ₂	543	δ SO ₂	546	δ SO ₂
513m		514	γ C19-N7	519	γ C19-N7				
	502 vw	500	τ R ₂ (A1)	505	τ wSO ₂	498	τ R ₂ (A1)	508	τ R ₂ (A2)
				497	γ C11-C16	495	τ R ₂ (A2);	499	τ R ₂ (A1)

							$\tau R_2(A1)$		
486 sh		488	$\gamma N6-C14$			488	$\tau R_2(A3)$	496	$\tau R_1(A3)$
	460 vw	438	$\tau R_2(A1);$ $\beta R_3(A2);$ $\tau R_3(A1)$	448	$\beta R_3(A2);$ $\tau R_2(A1)$	436	$\beta R_3(A2)$	446	$\beta R_3(A2)$
				415	$\tau R_3(A1)$				
	407 s	407	$\tau R_3(A1)$	409	$\tau R_3(A3)$	406	$\tau R_3(A1)$	405	$\tau R_3(A1)$
		404	$\tau R_3(A1)$	398	$\beta C19-N7$	383	$\beta N6-C14$	395	$\beta C19-N7$
	382 w	386	$\beta C19-N7$	385	$\beta N6-C14$	381	$\beta C19-N7;$	381	τwSO_2
	375 w	379	$\delta C11C16N7$	379	$\beta R_3(A2)$	370	$\tau R_3(A3)$	375	$\tau R_3(A3)$
	350 w	344	$\rho C16-C11$			343	τwSO_2	366	$\rho C16-C11$
		342	$\beta R_2(A2);$ τwSO_2	347	$\beta R_2(A2)$	334	$\beta C12=O4$	349	$\beta R_2(A2)$
	317 w	337	$\beta R_3(A2)$	339	$\beta C12-O4$	322	$\nu N7-C16$	334	$\nu C9-S1$
	290 w	288	ρSO_2	300	$\tau R_3(A1);$ ρSO_2	285	$\tau R_3(A1);$ ρSO_2	294	$\tau R_3(A1)$
		268	$\beta N6-C14$	271	ρSO_2	264	ρSO_2	263	ρSO_2
	253 w	244	$\nu C9-S1;$ $\beta R_3(A2);$ $\gamma N6-C14;$ τwSO_2	249	$\beta R_3(A2);$ $\beta N6-C14$	241	$\nu C9-S1$	247	$\beta N6-C14$
	211 m	215	$\tau R_2(A3)$	236	$\tau R_2(A3)$	216	$\gamma N7-H31;$ $\tau R_1(A3)$	229	$\tau R_2(A3)$
		196	$\beta C11-C16$	205	$\beta C11-C16$	203	$\beta R_2(A2)$	203	ρSO_2
	190 s	191	$\delta C16N7C19$	191	$\gamma C11-C16;$ $\beta C11-C16$			188	$\beta C11-C16$
						172	$\tau R_1(A3)$		
		175	τwCH_3	167	ButtC10-C9	161	τwCH_3	179	τwCH_3
	161 s	154	ButtC10-C9	162	τwCH_3	152	ButtC10-C9	166	ButtC10-C9
		125	$\tau R_1(A2)$	139	$\gamma N6-C14$	126	$\tau R_1(A2)$ $\gamma N6-C14$	144	$\gamma N6-C14$
				114	$\tau R_3(A2)$	105	$\gamma C11-C16$	113	$\gamma C11-C16$
		105	$\gamma C11-C16$	108	$\tau wC16-C11$	100	$\gamma N7-H31$	110	$\tau wC16-C11$
		98	$\gamma N7-H31;$ $\tau wN7-C19;$ $\tau wC16-C11;$			90	$\tau wN7-C19$		
		78	$\tau wN7-C19$	86	$\tau R_2(A2)$			90	$\tau R_2(A2);$ $\tau R_3(A2)$
				69	$\gamma N7-H31$			70	$\tau R_3(A2);$ $\gamma N7-H31$
		58	$\tau R_2(A2)$	59	$\delta C11C16N7$	57	$\tau R_2(A2)$	56	$\delta C11C16N7$
		54	$\tau R_3(A2)$			48	$\tau R_3(A2)$		
		32	$\tau wC16-C11$	36	$\tau wN7-C19$	30	$\tau wC16-C11$	29	$\tau wN7-C19$
		21	$\tau C16-N7$	24	$\tau C16-N7$	13	$\tau C16-N7$	22	$\tau C16-N7$

Abbreviations: ν , stretching; β deformation in the plane; γ deformation out of plane; wag, wagging; τ , torsion; βR , deformation ring τR , torsion ring; ρ , rocking; τw , twisting; δ , deformation; a, antisymmetric; s, symmetric; (A₁), benzyl Ring1; (A₂), thiazine Ring2; (A₃), pyridyl Ring3. ^aThis work, ^bFrom scaled quantum mechanics force field, ^cSpectraBase, n.d..

Band Assignments

4000-2000 cm^{-1} region. The O-H stretching modes of neutral and cation of piroxicam are assigned in different regions, as predicted by calculations, thus the shoulder at 3234 cm^{-1} and the Raman band at 3022 cm^{-1} are respectively assigned to those vibration modes. The N-H stretching modes of anion, neutral, zwitterion and cation are assigned to the IR bands at 3392 and 3311 cm^{-1} while the group of IR and Raman bands between 3178 and 2980 cm^{-1} are assigned to CH stretching modes of different rings of four species, as detailed in Table 13. The antisymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of CH_3 groups are assigned as predicted by SQM calculations between 3025 and 2874 cm^{-1} . As expected, the symmetric modes are predicted at lower wavenumbers than the corresponding antisymmetric ones (Iramain, et al., 2022; Sundius, & Brandán, 2023; Brandán, 2018)

2000-1000 cm^{-1} region. The two intense IR and Raman bands at 1647 and 1612 cm^{-1} are assigned to C=O stretching modes of four species while the group of IR bands between 1602 and 1548 cm^{-1} are attributed to C=C and C=N of benzyl, thiazine and pyridyl rings. The CH_3 deformation modes are predicted between 1441 and 1377 cm^{-1} while the rocking modes of these groups are predicted between 1194 and 1115 cm^{-1} . The antisymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of SO_2 groups are predicted in the four species in different regions, thus, the antisymmetric modes are predicted between 1270 and 1221 cm^{-1} while the symmetric modes between 1092 and 1030 cm^{-1} , as observed in Table 13. Hence, the IR and Raman bands between 1278 and 1221 cm^{-1} are assigned to antisymmetric modes while the symmetric modes are assigned to the bands between 1099 and 1031 cm^{-1} . The N6- CH_3

stretching modes present in all tropane alkaloids are also predicted by calculations in the four species of piroxicam in this region Brandán, 2018), thus, these modes are assigned between 1027 and 1001 cm^{-1} . Some deformations modes of benzyl (A1) rings are also predicted and assigned in this region (Iramain, et al., 2022; Sundius, & Brandán, 2023; Brandán, 2018).

1000-100 cm^{-1} region. The C-C and N-S stretching modes of thiazine rings are predicted between 776 and 750 cm^{-1} , hence, the strong IR band at 765 cm^{-1} can be assigned to those vibration modes of four species. The deformation and wagging modes of SO_2 groups are respectively predicted at $613/569$ and $546/543 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and, for these reasons, the IR and Raman bands between 615 and 535 cm^{-1} are assigned to those vibration modes. The rocking and twisting modes of SO_2 groups in the four species are predicted and assigned between 381 and 203 cm^{-1} although in the neutral species the twisting mode is also predicted at 505 cm^{-1} . Other skeletal vibration modes are predicted in this region, as the N-H, C-H, C-C, C-N and C=O deformations out-of-plane and deformations and torsions modes of three benzyls, thiazine and pyridyl rings.

Force Constants

The scaled internal force constants for the four species of piroxicam have been calculated in gas phase and aqueous solution by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method taking into account the harmonic force constants with the SQMFF approach and the Molvib program (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). Table 14 show these results for the four species in both media.

Table 14. Comparison of Main Scaled Internal Force Constants for the Four Species of Piroxicam in Gas and Aqueous Solution Phases

Piroxicam ^a								
Force constant	Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic	
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM
$f(\nu \text{O-H})$	-	-	5.047	5.107	-	-	5.909	5.517
$f(\nu \text{N-H})$	6.553	6.485	6.455	6.436	6.304	6.343	6.253	6.301

$f(\nu N-S)$	3.540	3.640	3.337	3.503	3.221	3.554	3.070	3.448
$f(\nu S-O)$	8.092	7.596	8.553	7.859	8.157	7.647	8.622	7.893
$f(\nu S-C)$	2.908	2.980	2.904	2.960	2.859	2.959	2.835	2.949
$f(\nu C=O)$	10.003	8.448	9.479	8.818	10.626	8.830	10.220	9.347
$f(\nu C-O)$	-	-	6.635	5.889	-	-	6.880	6.019
$f(\nu C-N)$	5.505	5.532	5.839	5.732	5.343	5.549	5.609	5.733
$f(\nu CH_3)$	4.795	4.876	4.850	4.910	4.835	4.885	4.868	4.912
$f(\nu C-H)$	5.080	5.162	5.143	5.177	5.166	5.216	5.198	5.229
$f(\delta CH_3)$	0.546	0.536	0.547	0.539	0.546	0.537	0.548	0.537
$f(\delta SO_2)$	1.655	1.599	1.621	1.589	1.656	1.603	1.614	1.594

Note: Units are $\text{mdyn } \text{\AA}^{-1}$ for stretching and $\text{mdyn } \text{\AA} \text{ rad}^{-2}$ for angle deformations. ^aThis work

Regarding the values presented in the table, it is observed that the cationic species present the higher $f(\nu O-H)$ force constants values in both media, as compared with the neutral species due to the lower O-H distances observed from Table 2 in the two media for the cationic species. Note that in both neutral and cationic species the OH groups present H bonds with the O atoms of C=O groups. The higher values observed in the $f(\nu N-H)$ force constants values of anionic species are justified by the lower N-H bond lengths predicted for this species while the lower N-S and S-C geometrical parameters values predicted for anion also justify its higher related force constants values. For the same reasons, the different force constants values observed in the different species are related to the diverse bond lengths and angles predicted by B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations.

Ultraviolet-Visible Spectrum

Predicted ultraviolet spectra of anionic, neutral, zwitterion and cationic species of piroxicam in aqueous solution by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method are shown in Figure 10

compared with the experimental ones recorded in ethanol and methanol solutions taken respectively from El-Shwiniy, (2020) and Studocu, (n.d.). Note that in Fig. 10 is presented only the spectrum in methanol taken from Studocu, (n.d.). Experimentally, according to El-Shwiniy, (2020) three bands at 408, 330 and 296 nm are observed although according to Studocu, (n.d.) the positions of bands change at 335, 241 and 223 nm. In the anion, two bands are predicted at 406 and 327 nm while in the other species three peaks are observed which are shown in Table 15 together with the oscillator strengths (f). Thus, the anion shows two bands at 406 and 327 nm, the neutral species three bands at 339, 263 and 249 nm, the zwitterion at 775, 469 and 355 nm while the cation at 433, 337 and 285 nm. These bands are attributed to those transitions predict by NBO calculations, such as $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions due to the presence of chromophores C=C, S=O, C=N bonds of benzyl, thiazine and pyridyl rings. The few differences observed could be associated to the solvents because the calculations were performed in water where the interactions solute-solvent or solvent-solvent were not considered.

Figure 10. Predicted Ultraviolet Spectra of Anionic, Neutral, Zwitterion and Cationic Species of Piroxicam in Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Method Compared with the Experimental in Methanol**
Source: Studocu, (n.d.)

Table 15. TD-DFT Calculated Visible Absorption Wavelengths (nm) and Oscillator Strengths (f) for the Four Species of Piroxicam in Aqueous Solution Compared with the Corresponding Experimental

6-311++G** ^a								Exp.	
Anionic		Neutral		Zwitterion		Cationic		Ref. ^b	Ref. ^c
λ (nm)	f	λ (nm)	f	λ (nm)	f	λ (nm)	f	λ (nm)	λ (nm)
406	0.1024	339	0.4960	775	0.0753	433	0.1604	335	408
327	0.1599	263	0.1039	469	0.1164	337	0.3295	241	330
-	-	249	0.1345	355	0.0390	285	0.2034	223	296

Note: ^aThis work, ^b Studocu, n.d., ^c El-Shwiniy, 2020.

Conclusions

In this work, structures of freebase or neutral, anionic, cationic and zwitterionic species of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory piroxicam agent have been optimised in gas phase and aqueous solution by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method.

The dipole moments vectors of all the species show different magnitudes and behaviours in solution suggesting different hydrations. Hence, the charged species cation and anion, are most hydrated in solution, as suggested by the tendency in its values: cation > anion > zwitterion > neutral or freebase.

The predicted geometrical parameters for the neutral species shows practically the same values in both media indicating that this form is less hydrated in water due to its lower solvation energy, low volume and dipole moment.

The hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory performs very good concordances between experimental and theoretical ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR, IR, Raman and ultraviolet spectra.

NBO and AIM calculations suggest that the neutral species presents higher stabilities in both media while the cation is the less stable species in aqueous solution probably due to its higher hydration.

The frontier orbitals studies show that the reactivity increase according the following order: neutral < cation < anion < zwitterion, thus, the zwitterion is the most reactive species in both media.

The very good correlations between experimental and theoretical ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR and ultraviolet spectra in solution suggest that all species are present in solution.

Here, complete assignments of all the species and their scaled internal force constants are reported for first time.

Author Contribution Statement

Elida Romano: Performed the experiments, Conceived and designed the experiments, Contributed reagents. Maximiliano A. Iramain: Performed the experiments, Analysis tools or data. Maria E. Manzur: Contributed reagents, materials. Silvia Antonia Brandán: Analysed and interpreted the data, Wrote the paper.

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Data Availability Statement

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of Interest Statement

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Silvia Antonia Brandán is part of the Editorial Board for Heliyon.

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Highlights

Four species of piroxicam were optimised by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations

The solvation energies follow the tendency: cation > anion > zwitterion > neutral

The neutral species is less hydrated in water due to its lower solvation energy

NBO and AIM calculations suggest that the cation is the less stable species in solution

The reactivity increase according: neutral < cation < anion < zwitterion